

THE CONCEPT OF ECONOMIC AND LEGAL CULTURE AND ITS INTERPRETATION

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Abstract. *The concept of economic and legal culture and its interpretation are one of the important aspects of economic and legal relations in modern society. This article analyzes in detail the essence, components of economic and legal culture and their role in society. The article shows the importance of economic laws and legal norms, as well as the role of moral values and social responsibility in economics and law. It also highlights the importance and methods of developing economic and legal culture. Through an analytical approach, the article helps to comprehensively understand the role of economic and legal culture in the life of the state and society. In particular, the article presents information not only about the main components of economic and legal culture, but also about their interdependence.*

Keywords: *culture, economic culture, economic consciousness, economic knowledge, legal culture, legal education, legal knowledge.*

Economic culture is the guarantee of our prosperous life,
Legal culture is the mechanism that regulates it!

INTRODUCTION. Today, ensuring the rule of law, strengthening the protection of the rights and interests of the individual, family, society and the state, increasing the legal culture and legal awareness of the population, educating citizens in the spirit of obedience and respect for the law is not only the goal, but also its means, the most important condition for building a truly democratic legal state and a free civil society based on a developed market economy. It is this economic and legal culture that serves to ensure economic stability, justice and normative values for citizens and society. Insufficient understanding of laws, their non-compliance, and lack of economic and legal knowledge create the need to develop a comprehensive set of conditions aimed at increasing economic and legal culture in society, especially among students of higher education. Economic problems can be associated with legal boundaries, which is a serious problem that hinders development. For this reason, a student who has graduated from higher education and entered professional activity must have economic and legal culture in order to find his place in society and live a prosperous lifestyle. It is no secret that a person with economic and legal culture can achieve great results not only in professional activity, but also in the family. Given the above reasons, it is important to understand the concept of culture in a broad sense before interpreting the concepts of economic and legal culture.

"Culture" (Arabic "madaniyat" - Medina, city, education) - a set of material and spiritual wealth created by people in the process of mastering and transforming nature and existence, as well as the ways and methods of restoring and building these wealth. Culture develops together with material and spiritual production, social and interpersonal relations, politics, family, morality, behavior, law, education, upbringing, creativity, science, service, lifestyle, etc., and reflects the level of development of society.

If we look at the general definition of culture, today it is difficult to find another social phenomenon in the social sciences where the concept of "culture" is so diverse, rich in contradictory interpretations and opinions. As an example, according to the calculations of foreign scholars, by 1919, seven definitions of the concept of "culture" had been given, by 1950 this number had reached 164, and in the 1970s - 250. American scholars A. Kroeber and K. Kluckhan noted that in the early 1950s there were 257 definitions of the concept of "culture".

In the social sciences, approaches to culture can be divided into three groups: anthropological, sociological, and philosophical.

The concept of culture is used in broad and narrow senses. In a broad sense, the concept of culture reflects the sum of all material and spiritual wealth created by mankind throughout the entire process of historical development. In a narrow sense, the concept of culture is used to express the level of spiritual and aesthetic life of society.

The term culture is used in a broad sense and means the set of achievements achieved by society in the production, social, and spiritual life, the level of such achievements achieved by a social group or people in a certain period, the sum of education, upbringing, intelligence, and enlightenment, and the conditions of life that meet the needs of an enlightened person. It is no coincidence that the year 2000 was declared the "International Year for the Culture of Peace" by the resolution of the UN General Assembly.

Cultural forms are mainly divided into three types: elite culture, folk culture and mass culture.

1. Elite culture (from the French word "the best") is the highest, privileged stratum that performs the functions of coordinating and developing the management aspects of any social structure. Theories about the elite were first described in the views of Plato, Aristotle, Nietzsche and others, and were brought to a systematic view at the beginning of the 20th century by V. Pareto, G. Mosca, Michels. In modern Western sociology, the elite is interpreted differently. In this, the elite is interpreted as the people who are oriented towards power, the most politically active (Mosca), the people who have the most prestige, status, and wealth in society, and who have intellectual and moral superiority over the masses (J. Ortega-i-Gasset), the part of society that differs from the uncreative majority (Toynbee), the most qualified specialists, managers, and senior officials in the management system (technological determinism).

The theory of elite is further developed in the works of the great contemporary sociologists Mills, Riesman, Bell. The culture of the elite (upper class population) is intended for the privileged strata of society. The rule of "art for art's sake" implies that culture includes fine art, classical music, and examples of fiction that only elites can read. Such examples of culture are complex and are created for representatives of high taste, who have a special intellectual and aesthetic status.

2. Folk culture is a culture that has grown up among the population and is created by individuals with extraordinary talent. The authors of folk art are usually unknown. These include legends, fairy tales, epics ("Gorughli", "Alpomish", etc.), which can be individual (for example, bakhshis), group (song or play performance), or public (for example, festivals, folk holidays).

3. Mass culture - cultural samples that were formed in the middle of the 20th century as a result of the deep penetration of mass communication and information media into the life of society and their availability to all social groups and are essentially understandable to the population of all ages (popular pop music, circus, etc.). Mass culture usually has less artistic value than folk or folk culture and is created with the aim of being mastered by the masses. In this regard, it is worth

noting that the idea of national independence “is of great importance to prevent the organization of activities in the spheres of culture and art on a completely commercial basis, to prevent the leading place of works of young people, which are ideologically and artistically shallow, and our national values. For this reason, it is important for each person to understand and study the components of economic and legal culture and its interdependence, to guarantee its achievement of economic and legal prosperity and stability.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY. Recently, there has been interest in studying the relationship between law and economics in more depth, and the work “Economics and Law” (authored by A.M. Nikitin, Yu.A. Tsipkin, N.D. Eriashvili, etc.) is being studied as a textbook for universities[1]. J.Y. Yizengaw and J.C. Weidman in their research report that Ethiopia needs a skilled workforce for economic development and social change, and that there may be various factors affecting the employability of engineering graduates in Ethiopia (the quality of the learning environment, the development of skills and competencies that are relevant to the curriculum)[2]. The issues of economic education have long historical roots and are reflected in the works of Eastern thinkers Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Nasr Al-Farabi, Amir Temur, Alisher Navoi, Abdurakhman Jami, Jalaluddin Davani, Husayn Voiz Kashifi, Ahmad Donish, and Abdullah Avloni. Our historical heritage contains many ideas about the importance and significance of economic ideas in the development of society, as well as the issues of providing economic education to young people and educating them on the principle of "teacher-student" [3].

Such great pedagogues and innovative teachers of the last century as P.P. Blonsky, N.A. Vyshnegradsky, S.I. Gessen, N.K. Krupskaya, P.F. Kapterev, A.S. Makarenko, N.I. Pirogov, K.D. Ushinsky, S.T. Shatsky made a great contribution to the study and development of the economic and legal culture of the individual. Their works address the problems of forming economic and legal culture among students in the conditions of historical changes in society, and propose methods and technologies that help educate patriotic citizens who know and respect existing rights. The socio-economic changes of the 20th century have focused the attention of the pedagogical community on the formation of economic and legal culture, an active civic position in young people striving for an independent life.

Psychological, pedagogical and general theoretical characteristics of the quality under study Yu.K. Vasilyeva, I.F. Isaeva, M.L. Levitsky, V.K. Rozova, V.A. Slastenina, A.N. Khodusova, E.N. Shyushova and others.

The works of foreign scientists S. Brew, M. Woodcock, C. Campbell, F. Kotler, D. Lindsay, K. Levi-Strauss, A. Maslow, K. McConnell, D. Rubinfeld, P. Hayney on the issues of economic and legal education of young people are of particular interest.

Also, the theoretical and practical foundations of our development are further enriched in a number of works aimed at developing accelerated development programs based on the principle of "open economy" and innovative ideas and technologies put forward by the President of our country Sh.M. Mirziyoyev. These program works make a great contribution to the development of economic theory and the increase in economic literacy. Of course, after independence, a number of books were published and scientific articles were published on the problem of economic education. Among the scientists S. S. Gulyamov, Sh. Z. Abdullaeva, A. Kadyrov, J. Jalolov, N. Tukhliev, A. Zheng, N. Beknzov and others can be mentioned. After independence, the friendly relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the Commonwealth countries, in particular the Russian Federation, and their interaction in various fields are taking deeper roots. We can see this

in the example of the Russian Academy of Economics named after G. A. Plekhanov, which is considered one of the most prestigious higher educational institutions in the world. It serves as a bridge in the development of economic education in Russia and Uzbekistan.

The book "Economic Theory", which is currently of great importance in economic education, was created in collaboration with prominent Russian scientists, in particular, the president of the academy, academician, V. I. Vidyapin, academician G. P. Zhuravlyova, as well as Uzbek scientists, academicians, S. S. Gulyomov, M. Sh. Sharifkhodjaev, Q. Abdurakhmonov. This book is widely used by economists of both countries [4].

As D.A. Kerimov noted: "Law is an objective reality as a system of certain legal norms in the existing society" [5]. A person actively interacts with the outside world, his consciousness is guided by a large amount of information, a mind that forms his understanding of the structures of legal reality. It unites the totality of legal phenomena and all interacting subjects. A person's perception of the surrounding reality allows him to form a holistic picture of the law, as a result of which legal thinking is formed.

From the above, it can be seen that the components of economic and legal culture and their interrelationships have not been fully studied.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. As we all know, today social relations are accelerating to such an extent that it is becoming increasingly difficult for people to perceive information and treat these social relations with a legal idealistic mood. This requires that all people be familiar with the current legal norms to the required level.

The main manifestations of economic and legal culture include: knowledge and compliance with regulatory and legal acts regulating the economic sphere of society (for example, the law-abiding actions of subjects of tax-paying trade relations and others); understanding of the cause-and-effect relationships in the sphere of legal and economic relations between subjects of a market economy (for example, property relations, anti-corruption actions, etc.); making decisions that contribute to the satisfaction of economic interests in the context of existing legal reality, etc.[6].

Economic culture. The economic culture of a society is a system of values and motives. It requires a special attitude to forms of ownership, improves the business environment. Economic culture is of decisive importance in the development of human economic activity and is an inseparable unity of consciousness and practical activity, manifested in the process of production, distribution and consumption.

Economic culture is called the set of material and spiritually socially developed means of activity, with the help of which the material and productive life of people is carried out.

The main components of economic culture are:

- economic consciousness
- economic behavior
- economic knowledge
- economic thinking
- economic literacy

These components form economic culture and are of great importance in the development of society.

Economic consciousness. The basis of the economic culture of a person is economic consciousness. Economic consciousness is the basis of the economic culture of mankind. Economic consciousness is the sum of the experiences, knowledge and understanding of an

individual or society about economic processes. It plays an important role in making decisions in economic activity.

Economic consciousness includes such aspects as knowledge of economic laws, market mechanisms and economic systems, economic phenomena and their impact on social life, the ability to effectively allocate resources and make choices between options, creativity and efficiency in solving economic problems, a conscious approach to economic activity and its impact on society. With the growth of economic consciousness, individuals and societies can achieve economic success.

Economic behavior. Behavioral economics studies the biases, tendencies and heuristics that influence the decisions people make in order to improve, change or restructure traditional economic theory. It helps to determine whether people make good or bad choices and helps them make better choices. It can be applied both before and after a decision is made. This concept is related to psychology, sociology, and other social sciences in addition to economic theory. Behavioral economics is a branch of economics that focuses on the study of economic decisions and behavior.

Behavioral economics includes the following main aspects and differs from the traditional economic model in that it more closely reflects the actual behavior of people. It analyzes people's behavior in relation to their economic decisions, their interests and goals, how emotions, intuitive thinking and social influences affect economic decisions, the impact of government economic policies and regulations on human behavior is studied, and people often make wrong decisions by ignoring probabilities.

The behavioral economics approach differs from the traditional economic model in that it more closely reflects the actual behavior of people[7].

Economic knowledge. Economic knowledge is a key component of economic culture. They allow us to develop our understanding of the basic laws of the development of the economy of society, economic relations in the world around us, to develop our economic thinking and practical skills, to form economically sound, morally justified behavior. Economic knowledge is a set of human economic ideas about the production, distribution, exchange and consumption of material goods, forms and methods that contribute to the sustainable development of society, and its impact on the formation of economic processes. They are an important component of economic culture. Economic knowledge forms an idea of the laws of development of economic relations in the world around us, the economic life of society. On their basis, economic thinking and practical skills of economically literate, morally sound behavior, important economic qualities of a person in modern conditions are developed.

Economic thinking. Economic thinking plays an important role in a person's economic culture, which allows them to understand the essence of economic phenomena and processes, correctly use the acquired economic concepts, and analyze specific economic situations. Economic thinking is the process of understanding and solving economic problems. It mainly includes issues such as resource allocation, production, consumption, and economic growth.

Core values:

1. Allocation: Efficient allocation of resources.
2. Decision-making: Analyzing problems and finding the most optimal solutions.
3. Economic models: Understanding interconnections.
4. Guarantees: Competition and market mechanisms.

Economic thinking stimulates creative thinking and the use of innovations in the production process, which leads to economic growth. This process is also important in increasing the well-being of society.

An important component of a person's economic culture is economic thinking... It allows you to obtain information about the essence of economic phenomena and processes, work with studied economic concepts, and analyze specific economic situations.

Economic literacy. Economic literacy, economic culture are an important aspect of a person's spirituality. Because knowledge of economics allows you to organize and effectively run an economy, to make a profit. An important component of a person's economic culture is economic thinking ... It allows you to obtain information about the essence of economic phenomena and processes, to work with the studied economic concepts, and to analyze specific economic situations. In addition to teaching targeted knowledge, it is important to form educationally important knowledge and skills such as industriousness, thrift, a sense of responsibility and accountability for property, the implementation of innovative ideas that are useful for oneself and society, a responsible approach to work and tasks, entering into economic and social relations with people, honesty, piety, patronage, protection, the duties and responsibilities of parents to their children and children to their parents, the laws, rules and standards for conducting entrepreneurship, trade and other economic activities, and adherence to the principles of mutual partnership in economic and social cooperation. For example, the meaning of thrift alone refers not only to saving material goods or money, but also to using time effectively, mobilizing existing opportunities for positive activities, refraining from undesirable habits and practices, useless and wasteful spending, as well as focusing scientific and intellectual potential on research and solutions to projects that are beneficial to humanity and society[8].

The components of economic and legal culture are: economic knowledge, legal knowledge, moral values, strong social traditions, practical skills and social responsibility.

These components play an important role in the formation and development of economic and legal culture.

The interrelationship of the components that make up economic and legal culture:

Legal culture. Legal culture is a sphere of freedom, it allows a person to assert himself; At the same time, legal culture educates discipline and responsibility, without which there is no

freedom in society. In the process of democratic changes, the role of legal culture has increased significantly, its tasks contribute to a deep transformation of all aspects of life[9].

Legal culture is a set of concepts that form legal norms, values, opinions and relationships in society. It, first of all, ensures legal relations between citizens and state bodies.

Legal culture also includes: citizens and organizations should have sufficient information about their rights and obligations, respect for law in society and an understanding of its importance, the effectiveness and fairness of the legal system.

The main components of legal culture are:

- legal awareness
- legal education
- legal knowledge
- legal thinking
- legal literacy

These components form legal culture and are of great importance in the development of the individual and society.

Legal awareness is one of the forms of social consciousness, a set of ideas, feelings, and perceptions that people have about law, legislation, law and order, and other legal phenomena. It is a person's knowledge, concepts, and understanding of the legal system and laws and how to apply them in society. This awareness also includes knowledge of one's rights and obligations as a citizen and being a citizen, and how to act in solving legal problems.

The category of legal awareness serves as such a concept that expresses a separate dimension of legal reality. Legal awareness actively influences the regulation of all diverse life processes in society and the state, mobilizes the public for creative work, and contributes to the maintenance and strengthening of public order. A high level of legal awareness in society and a respectful attitude of citizens to the law are the key to a democratic state and the effective functioning of the political and legal system. Legal consciousness is one of the types of social consciousness. There are various forms of social consciousness, with the help of which people understand the environment and society. There is political, moral (spiritual), aesthetic, ethical, religious, legal consciousness. Legal consciousness is the sum of the views, perceptions, feelings, assessments, and mental attitudes of members of society about law and about legal phenomena that actually exist in social life.

Legal education is the process of developing a person's legal knowledge, understanding and reasoning. It helps, first of all, to understand the rights and obligations of citizens. Through legal education, people learn how to use the legal system, comply with the law and protect their rights.

This process can be carried out in schools, universities, legal organizations and public institutions.

Legal education has its own history. In Ancient Greece and Ancient Rome, legal education began to be instilled in the population from a young age. For example, in Ancient Rome, children had to memorize 12 copper tables by the time they reached adulthood, that is, by the age of 14.

There is a unique system of legal education. These are:

- Preschool legal education.
- Legal education at school.
- Legal education in secondary specialized education.

- Legal education in higher education.
- Extracurricular legal education

Legal education also fosters legal culture, timely understanding and respect for laws in society. As a result, it increases civic responsibility and contributes to building a just society.

Legal knowledge. Legal knowledge is the initial knowledge in the field of law, basic concepts, understanding of the legal system and laws. This knowledge includes knowledge of the laws and regulations of the state, information about the legal structure and its functions in each state, legal terms, such as civil, criminal, contractual, and understanding how to apply legal norms and laws.

Legal knowledge helps citizens to increase their legal awareness, protect their rights, and solve legal problems. This knowledge improves the legal literacy of a person, as well as social activities.

Legal thinking. Legal thinking is the consciousness formed on the basis of law and its guiding star. It is widely used in legal practice, in the teaching of legal sciences, in legal education and propaganda. This thinking has its own characteristics and is expressed in the manifestation of fairness, accuracy, deep understanding of the essence of legal norms, and the ability to perceive the law [10]. Legal thinking is the ability to analyze, evaluate and solve legal and legal issues. It includes the following main aspects: understanding legal norms and laws, as well as their content, studying legal issues and situations, evaluating them logically, developing legal points of view designed to solve problems, assessing the practical significance and impact of laws and legal norms, and clearly and fluently expressing legal ideas, exchanging views on legal issues with other persons. Legal thinking is an integral element of social life, it finds expression in all aspects of social life. It also finds its reflection in relation to the whole person and in relation to the law, predetermines the actions of the person and accordingly shapes his activities.

Legal literacy. According to the CONCEPT of improving legal culture in society, legal literacy is the basis of legal culture. In order to ensure the supremacy of the Constitution and laws in the life and activities of society, it is necessary to create the foundations of legal knowledge. The legal culture and legal literacy of the population, first of all, ensure respect for the Constitution and laws [11]. This means that a superficial attitude to legal norms should not be the only idea. Respect for the law should be a deep belief in the heart of every person. It should be instilled and strengthened in the consciousness of a person from a young age. This is a huge, painstaking work of parents, preschool institutions, schools, all public associations and state organizations, and the entire society. Legal norms about what is possible and what is not are known to everyone. Understanding that the law cannot be broken should be the "eye of the heart" of the legal worldview.

A person with a perfect economic culture approaches economic problems in his daily life from the point of view of thrift. This is of great importance for the economic development of society.

For example, a person who has little knowledge of economic laws will never be indifferent to the harm caused by a leaking water pipe or a light bulb that is left burning in vain, to the crumbs of bread that are found underfoot due to the indiscretion of some individuals, to the pollution of comfortable streets and sidewalks that have been cleaned with great difficulty. "Little by little, there will be a lake," say our wise people. Similarly, it is inevitable that water that has become a lake will gradually disappear. If we summarize and bring to a common denominator the economic

opportunities that are being wasted, not yielding the desired results, and are being wasted in our country due to the weakness of economic consciousness, there is no doubt that a powerful wave will emerge from the fruits of economic knowledge. If this powerful wave is coordinated with the well-thought-out macroeconomic policy of the state and moves in one direction, the miracle of economic development that our people dream of will occur [12].

The relationship between economic consciousness and legal consciousness is a complex and complementary process. Economic consciousness, that is, people's understanding of economic problems, can directly affect their legal consciousness. For example, economic inequalities and problems can lead to changes in the legal system, the adoption of new laws. In addition, legal consciousness shapes economic consciousness, since laws and regulations determine how people carry out their economic activities. As a result, these two concepts influence and are interconnected, and also play an important role in the development of society.

CONCLUSION. The development of economic and legal culture helps society better adapt to economic processes, which ensures stability, increasing legal culture helps citizens better understand their rights and obligations, which strengthens social order, increases citizen activity in economic and legal issues, provides support to state leaders with requests and proposals, economic and legal culture supports innovative ideas, which opens up new opportunities for business, increases social justice by ensuring the protection of rights and economic equality.

There is a deep interdependence between economic and legal culture and its components. This interdependence determines the economic activity of individuals and their values. Legal culture, in turn, helps to respect, understand and apply laws and norms. Economic problems and requirements give impetus to the development of legal norms, and new economic conditions require updating existing laws. Economic and legal culture ensures stability in society. Economic development and legal protection play an important role together. The development of economic and legal consciousness is carried out through education, which forms the general culture of society. These factors further strengthen and develop economic and legal culture.

Also, economic and legal knowledge, upbringing, consciousness and thinking form people with a high level of economic and legal culture, who are able to legally regulate economic relations in society. Such people contribute to the stability and development of society.

Also, the importance of economic and legal knowledge:

- Decision-making: Good economic and legal knowledge helps to make clear and informed decisions.
- Avoidance of violations: Legal knowledge helps to avoid legal liability.
- Risk management: Economic knowledge facilitates the assessment of potential risks and opportunities.
- Efficiency: Allows for efficiency and competitive advantage.
- Innovation and entrepreneurship: Supports the development of new ideas and their legal implementation.

A student who does not have economic and legal knowledge in society cannot become an economically and legally educated and professionally cultured person in his work. In particular, in order to improve the economic and legal culture of students, it is advisable to include subjects that affect the formation of legal culture in the curricula of educational institutions, as well as to establish an effective social cooperation mechanism between civil society institutions, law enforcement agencies and the media. In this regard, it is appropriate to talk about the formation of

an economic and legal culture that allows students of higher education institutions to navigate the flow of economic and legal information, understand the root causes of legal imbalances in the economy, know the basic principles of legislation, know the principles of the transitional period of state economic policy and, on this basis, determine the economic and cultural rights of citizens.

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